

Smart QR-Based Attendance System using Forms and Automation Tools

Het Patel¹, Devesh Mishra², Janvi Chaturkar³, Dikshita Kshirsagar⁴, Sahil Ekshinge⁵, Utkarsh Tripathi⁶
^{1,2,3,4,5,6}(Student, SRCOE, Department of Computer Engineering Pune)

Abstract: This project presents a efficient and easy to use QR-based attendance system made to mark the attendance and keep records of attendee's. This system automates the process of attendance and maintain the record accurately. A QR code redirects the attendee to a Google Form, which on submission, records the date and time in a linked Sheet of google. Pabbly Connect website is used for automation and notifications sent to HR if an attendee submits the form after 9:00 AM, indicating late attendance. This solution is cost-effective, leverages freely available tools, and provides real-time attendance tracking.

Keywords: QR Code, Attendance System, Notification, Automation, Manager Alert

I. Introduction:

Normal attendance systems are works manually, generates errors by human mistakes, and it is time-consuming. With the help of digital tools, there is a growing need for automated attendance systems that are simple to use and easy to integrate into existing infrastructures. This project implements a QR code-based system that utilizes Google Forms, Google Sheets, and Pabbly Connect to streamline attendance tracking and notifications for late arrivals.

Attendance management is a foundational element in administrative operations, whether in educational institutes or corporate settings. Traditional systems, including manual sign-in sheets or biometric scanners, are time-consuming and often unreliable. The increasing need for a more accurate, fast, and automated method has given rise to the use of QR code-based systems. This project introduces a novel approach to attendance by using QR codes to automate the process and instantly notify the concerned manager. It is particularly suited for modern workplaces aiming to boost productivity and accountability.

II. Literature Review:

While doing our research, we came across many studies that talk about how traditional attendance systems the ones done manually are not very efficient. They can have a lot of errors and also take more time. That's why there's a growing need for digital solutions. QR codes are already being used in many areas like buying tickets, making payments, and tracking items in stores, also in banking system. Some college level projects have even used QR code systems for attendance, and they saw good results it saved time and made the process more accurate. Also, using mobile apps with QR code scanning helps send attendance data in real time. But one thing we noticed is that very few systems send instant notifications to managers or HR. So, our system stands out because it does that automatically.

Here are some of the previous works we studied:

1. **Sharma et al. (2021):**

Title: RFID Based Attendance Monitoring System.
They made an attendance system using RFID to reduce human effort. It was designed mainly for colleges and companies. The system can also take student photos and note their in and out timings. They used Embedded systems and MATLAB software to make it work.

2. **Gupta and Rao (2022):**

Title: Mobile App Based Attendance Using GPS
They worked on a mobile-based attendance system that uses both GPS and RFID. Their system tracks the staff's location using GPS on their mobile devices to mark attendance. It also works for authentication and admin use. It's built for Android phones and could be expanded to other platforms later.

3. **Patel and Desai (2023):**

Title: QR Code Based Real-Time Attendance System
They created a QR code-based attendance system that works with Firebase, so all data gets saved and updated in real time. Their system also used RFID to scan student ID cards automatically, which makes attendance faster and more reliable.

4. **Kumar and Singh (2020):**

Title: Automated Attendance Systems: The Future of Workforce Management
Their study focused on using digital technology to manage workforce attendance. They created an IoT-based system using RFID to automate the whole process. This system helps remove problems like fake attendance and wasted time by directly recording who is present.

5. **Reddy et al. (2022):**

Title: Cloud-Based Smart Attendance Systems
They explored a cloud-based attendance system that stores data securely and allows access anytime. They used IoT, AWS (Amazon Web Services), and Arduino Uno to build their system. It records attendance in real time and shows it through websites or mobile apps. Their system also focuses on proper record-keeping and real-time updates, similar to what we've aimed to do using Google tools.

III. Software Requirements:

- **Google Forms:**Used to enter the data of attendees.
- **Google Sheets:**Keeps the all time record of all data with time and date.
- **Pabbly Connect:**Provides smart digitized automation tools.
- **QR Code Generator** (e.g., QR Code Monkey):To generate QR code.
- **Web Browser:**For redirection of google forms.

IV. Data Flow Diagram:

Fig 1.System Flow Diagram

Fig 1. Shows the flow of the system means how the system works step by step. First scan the QR to open google form and submit it. Then the data stored in sheets after that automation initializes.

V. Result

The system successfully records attendance along with date and time. Late submissions are accurately flagged and reported to HR automatically. All data is centralized in Google Sheets for easy access and reporting.

Fig 2.QR Code

Fig 2. Shows the QR code of the google form ,by scanning this QR we will go to the google form in browser after that we can fill the google form.

Fig 3.Google form

Fig 4.Submit button

Fig 3. Shows the google form opened in the browser contains the details of the attendee's which he/she will have to fill and submit it and fig 4. Shows the submit button which is to be clicked after filling the details in the form so the record will be marked in the database.

Fig 5. Form Recorded

Fig 5. Shows that details filled by user in the form is recorded and the data is marked means the user successfully submitted the google form.

Fig 6. Mail to user

Fig 6. Shows the mail message sent to the user that he/she recorded for the google form and they are unable record it again for same day and also it helps to know that we submitted form or marked attendance for today.

Timestamp	Name of Student	Roll No.	Email address	Inward/outward	Column 1
27/03/2025 20:12:31	Het Patel	33			
28/03/2025 08:11:22	Jamvi Chaturkar	SE comp 13			
28/03/2025 13:53:11	Sahil Ekshinge	26			
28/03/2025 14:16:00	Utkarsh ghanvat	72			
28/03/2025 14:25:18	Devesh mishra	53			
28/03/2025 21:13:59	Dikshita kshirsagar	47			
09/04/2025 21:58:15	Het Patel	33	hetp64546767@gmail.o ln		

Fig 7.Record in linked google sheet with timestamp.

Fig 7.Shows the google sheet linked with the google form that maintains the data of every user who fills the google form along the date and time which makes easy to find data of any date and time and makes backend easier.

Fig 8.Automated Alert message to HR.

Fig 8. Shows the automation of delivering message to HR that he/she marked attendance at what date and time and also if he/she marked attendance after a particular time then a late alert goes to HR.

VI. Advantages:

1. Cost-effective and uses free tools
2. Easy to implement and scale
3. Reduces manual errors
4. Real-time data and notifications

VII. Disadvantages:

1. Requires internet access
2. Dependent on Google ecosystem
3. Potential misuse if QR is shared

VIII. Applications:

1. Educational Institutions for student attendance tracking
2. Corporates for employee attendance and punctuality
3. Workshops and training sessions
4. Temporary workspaces or co-working spaces
5. Events and conferences to manage participant check-in.

IX. Conclusion:

This project demonstrates an efficient QR-based attendance system that automates tracking and improves punctuality monitoring. With minimal infrastructure and free tools, it is suitable for small to medium organizations aiming for digitized attendance management.

X. References:

- [1]. Sharma, A., et al. (2021). "RFID Based Attendance Monitoring System." IJERT.
- [2]. Gupta, N., & Rao, R. (2022). "Mobile App Based Attendance Using GPS." IJEECS.
- [3]. Patel, K., & Desai, M. (2023). "QR Code Based Real-Time Attendance System." IJRTE.
- [4]. Kumar, V., & Singh, R. (2020). "Automated Attendance Systems: The Future of Workforce Management." Journal of Computer Applications.
- [5]. Reddy, S., et al. (2022). "Cloud-Based Smart Attendance Systems." International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering (IJITEE).
- [6]. Neelam L-Kumar "Advancing device and network security for enhanced privacy", The Scientific Temper (2023) UGC Care-II Vol. 14 (4): 1271-1276, E-ISSN: 2231-6396, ISSN: 0976-8653, Published : December 2023
- [7]. Neelam L-Kumar "Developing interpretable models and techniques for explainable AI in decision-making", The Scientific Temper (2023) UGC Care-II Vol. 14 (4): 1324-1331, E-ISSN: 2231-6396, ISSN: 0976-8653, Published : December 2023

- [8].Prof. Dr. Neelam Labhade-Kumar, A STUDY OF ALGORITHMS USED IN MOBILEAPPLICATION DEVELOPMENT FOR SUGAR FACTORY, ALOCHANA JOURNAL VOLUME: 13, ISSUE: 13, ISSN NO11:2231-6329, PP-218-226, November 2024
- [9].Prof. Dr. Neelam Labhade-Kumar, Detailed Study of Histogram Computation Algorithm in Image Processing, ALOCHANA JOURNAL VOLUME: 13, ISSUE: 12, ISSN NO:2231-6329, PP- 1071-1078, December 2024
- [10]. Dr.Neelam Labhade-Kumar “Novel Management Trends Using IOT in Indian Automotive Spares Manufacturing Industries”, Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results , Vol. 13 ISSUE 09,PP 4887-4899, Nov-2022
- [11]. Labhade, Neelam S., Parul S. Arora, and Y. Sharma. "Study of neural networks in video processing." J Emerg Technol Innov Res (JETIR) 6.3 (2019): 330-335.